

АНАЛІЗ ЗВ'ЯЗКУ МІЖ СОМАТОФОРМНИМ СИМПТОКОМПЛЕКСУ ТА ДЕПРЕСІВНИМИ РОЗЛАДАМИ

ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE SOMATOFORM SYMPTOM COMPLEX AND DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS

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Introduction. Depressive disorders can be accompanied by a wide range of specific symptom complexes and comorbid conditions that modify the course of the disease. Despite the heterogeneity of the clinical picture of depressive disorders, they are always to some extent associated with somatic symptoms or the phenomenon of somatization. It is difficult to draw the line between the symptoms of the comorbid somatoform disorder and somatic symptoms of depression as they are both deeply interconnected. The selection of the somatoform symptom complex as a concomitant to depressive disorder diagnostic unit allows for assessing the composition of somatic symptoms and is necessary for the choice of different treatment tactics and the application of precision-oriented medicine.

Objective. To assess the relationship between the severity of depression and demographic factors to the number of complaints related to somatic symptoms in patients with depressive disorders.

Material and methods. The study included 186 patients with neurotic register depressive disorders and somatoform symptoms aged 18 to 50 years. The severity of somatic symptoms was assessed using the PHQ-15 patient health questionnaire, and the severity of depression was determined using the PHQ-9 patient health questionnaire. Binary logistic regression analysis was performed.

Results and discussion. Patients with more somatic symptoms had higher rates of depressive disorder (OR = 1,942, $p < 0,001$, CI = 1,648-2,589) and a higher frequency of rehospitalizations (OR = 1,206, $p < 0,05$, CI = 1,089-1,583). Being female (OR = 1,091, $p < 0,05$, CI = 1,027-1,486) and higher age (OR = 1,280, $p < 0,001$, CI = 1,207-1,434) are associated with manifestations of a more severe somatoform symptom complex.

Conclusion. The severity of the somatoform symptom complex is directly related to the severity of the depressive disorder and the number of rehospitalizations. These are the exact factors that indicate a more severe course of depressive disorder, its future chronicity and

the risk of disability. Choosing the right therapeutic approaches and taking into account the specifics of a somatoform syndrome, can help to improve treatment and improve prognosis.